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NIGERIA'S SOLID MINERALS POLICY AND ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT FOR INDIGENOUS BRASS ARTISANS IN NIGER STATE

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Abstract: Nigeria's renewed drive to diversify its economy through solid mineral development has intensified interest in how mineral governance translates into inclusive outcomes for downstream indigenous industries. However, empirical evidence on artisanal value chains dependent on mineral-based raw materials remains scarce. This study investigated the influence of Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State, Nigeria. Anchored in the Capability Approach and Global Value Chain theory, economic empowerment is conceptualized as access to raw materials, income stability, productive capacity, finance, market participation, and institutional inclusion. A mixed-methods descriptive design was adopted; combining survey data from 215 brass artisans in Bida with key informant interviews involving regulators, mining stakeholders, raw-material actors, and artisan representatives. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, mean scores, and chi-square tests, while qualitative data were examined thematically. Results indicate that the policy has had limited tangible effect on artisans' economic empowerment, particularly regarding raw-material affordability, credit access, income growth, and production expansion. Persistent reliance on informal intermediaries, restricted access to mineral buying centres, low policy awareness, and weak institutional coordination further constrain artisans' integration into the mineral governance framework. The study concludes that policy intent has not adequately translated into workshop-level outcomes, underscoring a structural disconnect between national mineral governance and grassroots artisanal livelihoods. It recommends a targeted artisan-support framework and a formal mineral-artisan linkage platform to strengthen raw-material access, financing, technological capacity, and artisan participation in mineral-sector governance.

Keywords: Solid Minerals Policy; Economic Empowerment; Brass Artisans; Mineral Value Chain; Capability Approach; Niger State.

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1. Introduction

Natural-resource governance has become a major development concern in resource-rich economies because mineral resources are increasingly viewed not only as sources of public revenue, but also as instruments for industrialization, employment generation, domestic value addition, and inclusive growth. In Nigeria, the need to diversify the economy away from oil dependence has made the solid mineral sector an important policy priority. Kabiru (2020), argues that Nigeria's overdependence on oil has reinforced the need for more diversified growth pathways in agriculture, solid mineral, and renewable energy. Similarly, Anyanwu and Uwazie (2024) observe that Nigeria's export-diversification challenge is linked to the country's continued dependence on oil exports at the expense of other productive sectors, including agriculture, mining, and solid minerals.

Nigeria's response to this challenge is reflected in key policy and regulatory instruments, including the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, the National Minerals and Metals Policy, and the Roadmap for the Growth and Development of the Nigerian Mining Industry. (Federal Ministry of Mines and Steel Development, 2016). These frameworks seek to improve sector governance, attract investment, formalise artisanal and small-scale mining, promote value addition, and strengthen the contribution of solid minerals to national development. However, the expected transformation of the sector has remained limited. Ifem et al. (2021), in their study on Nigeria's solid minerals industry, describe the sector as one characterised by a paradox of resource abundance and weak developmental outcomes. This position is consistent with NEITI's solid minerals reporting, which shows that the sector has continued to contribute less than 1% to national GDP despite its resource potential and reform attention (NEITI, 2023).

A major limitation of mineral-sector reform in Nigeria is that policy discussions often focus on extraction, licensing, revenue generation, and export performance, while giving limited attention to downstream indigenous producers who depend on mineral-based raw materials. Yet, the economic value of solid mineral is not realized only through extraction. It is also realized when mineral inputs are processed, transformed, and linked to domestic production systems. This makes indigenous craft industries important to the wider mineral value chain, particularly where they provide livelihoods, preserve cultural skills, and create local employment.

Bida brass-smithing in Niger State represents one of such downstream indigenous production systems. The craft supports artisans, apprentices, traders, households, and local markets, while also preserving an important aspect of Nupe cultural heritage. Its sustainability depends largely on reliable and affordable access to metal inputs such as brass, copper, aluminium-based materials, and other mineral-related resources. Where mineral governance reforms do not create effective linkages between extraction, raw-material aggregation, processing, financing, and local production, artisans may remain excluded from the benefits expected from solid mineral development.

Therefore, this study, examines the influence of Nigeria's solid minerals policy on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State. It does not assume that policy alone explains the economic condition of the artisans. Rather, it recognises that raw-material access, income stability, and production capacity may also be shaped by market prices, purchasing power, informal intermediaries, technology gaps, foreign-exchange pressures, and weak institutional coordination. The study is consequently positioned as an empirical assessment of how solid minerals policy implementation relates to artisan-level economic outcomes within a wider governance and market environment.

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1.2 Statement of the Problem

The economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State should be reflected in stable income, reliable raw material access, improved production capacity, market expansion, and institutional support. Following the implementation of Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy and related reforms, artisans in historic craft centres such as Bida are expected to benefit from predictable mineral input supply, affordable production costs, skills development, and inclusion in mineral sector governance. These outcomes would strengthen household livelihoods, sustain job creation through apprenticeships, preserve indigenous craftsmanship, and support subnational economic diversification.

Field realities, however, suggest a persistent gap between this policy expectation and artisan level outcomes. Brass artisans continue to contend with income instability, rising input costs, and production constraints, relying heavily on informal recycling and intermediary networks that fuel supply disruptions and price volatility (21st Century Chronicle, 2021). This fragility endures despite a reform agenda explicitly designed to promote diversification, formalisation, value addition, and local participation in mineral based production (Federal Ministry of Mines and Steel Development [FMMSD], 2016), and is further reflected in the limited contribution of the solid minerals sector to national output relative to its resource potential (NEITI, 2024; Ifem et al., 2021). Interventions such as cooperative formalisation, licensing reform, illegal mining control, local processing promotion, and mineral title administration aim to strengthen sector productivity and governance. Yet downstream artisans remain largely outside their reach. Informal channels continue to dominate raw material access, formal mineral markets remain poorly linked to craft producers, and implementation frequently overlooks non mining indigenous actors whose livelihoods depend on mineral inputs. This posits that there is limited evidence on how Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy translates into economic empowerment for downstream indigenous producers such as Bida's brass artisans, a clear empirical gap this study addresses by examining the policy's influence on raw material access, income stability, production capacity, and integration into the mineral governance framework.

1.3 Research Questions

- I. To what extent has Nigeria Solid Minerals Policy influenced the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger state, Nigeria?
- II. What Challenges hinder the effective integration of indigenous brass artisans into the solid minerals governance framework in Niger State, Nigeria?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- I. To assess the influence of Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy on the economic empowerment of Niger State indigenous brass artisans in Niger state, Nigeria.
- II. To identify the challenges hindering the effective integration of indigenous brass artisans into the solid MGF in Niger State, Nigeria.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

- I. **H₀₁:** Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy has no significant influence on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State, Nigeria.
- II. **H₀₂:** There are no significant challenges hindering the effective integration of indigenous brass artisans into the solid minerals governance framework in Niger State, Nigeria.

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2. Literature Review

2.1 Clarification of Conceptual

Solid minerals policy refers to the set of laws, regulations, institutional arrangements, and development strategies through which a state governs mineral resource exploration, extraction, processing, and utilisation to achieve economic, social, and environmental objectives. In development terms, such policy frameworks are expected to move mineral resources beyond extraction by promoting value addition, employment generation, industrial linkages, environmental protection, and inclusive participation in mineral-based economic activities (UNECA, 2011; FMMSD, 2016). In Nigeria, this policy direction is reflected in the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, the National Minerals and Metals Policy, and the Roadmap for the Growth and Development of the Nigerian Mining Industry, which emphasise formalisation, investment promotion, local processing, revenue generation, and the repositioning of solid minerals as a tool for economic diversification (FMMSD, 2016; NESG, 2023).

The relevance of this policy framework is linked to Nigeria's long-standing concern with oil dependence and the underperformance of non-oil sectors. Ifem et al. (2021), in their study published in the *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, describe Nigeria's solid minerals sector as one marked by the paradox of resource abundance and limited developmental outcomes. Their study shows that, despite various government interventions, the sector has not achieved its expected contribution to broad-based economic transformation. This position is consistent with NEITI's sector reporting, which indicates that solid minerals have continued to make a relatively small contribution to national output when compared with the sector's resource potential.

Artisanal and small-scale mining is an important component of mineral economies in many developing countries. It is generally characterised by labour-intensive production, limited capital, simple technology, weak formalisation, and strong links to rural livelihoods. Hilson and McQuilken (2014) observe that artisanal and small-scale mining in sub-Saharan Africa has received decades of policy and donor attention, but many interventions have failed to move operators out of poverty because they focus more on legalisation than on the practical livelihood constraints facing miners. In Nigeria, Otoijamun et al. (2021) similarly show that artisanal mining is affected by weak institutional support, inadequate technology, poor financing, and limited sustainability planning. These issues are important because weaknesses in upstream mineral governance can affect not only miners but also downstream producers who depend on mineral-based raw materials.

Indigenous brass-smithing represents one of such downstream production systems. In Bida, Niger State, brass-smithing is both a livelihood activity and a cultural heritage practice. The craft supports artisans, apprentices, traders, households and local markets, while also preserving traditional production knowledge. Alhassan et al. (2020), in their study on traditional crafts in Bida and Gusau, show that indigenous craft production in these towns is sustained largely through apprenticeship, informal knowledge transfer and locally organised production systems. Bida is also widely recognised for its craft traditions, including brass-smithing, glassmaking, metallurgy, wood carving and other folk-art practices, a status reflected in its recognition as a UNESCO Creative City of Crafts and Folk Art in 2021. Recent media evidence further suggests that brass artisans in Bida have increasingly turned to aluminium and other substitute materials because of high material costs, weak demand and limited government support, indicating the vulnerability of the craft to raw-material and market constraints. (21st Century Chronicle, 2021)

Economic empowerment, in the context of this study, refers to the ability of brass artisans to sustain and improve their livelihoods through reliable access to productive resources, stable income, improved production capacity,

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access to finance, market participation, and institutional support. This understanding is consistent with Sen's Capability Approach, which views development as the expansion of people's real freedoms and capabilities to live the kind of lives they value, rather than merely an increase in income (Sen, 1999). It also aligns with Kabeer's view that empowerment involves access to resources, the ability to exercise agency, and the achievement of valued outcomes (Kabeer, 1999). Therefore, empowerment is not limited to income alone; it includes the capacity of artisans to obtain raw materials at affordable prices, use improved tools, expand output, withstand market shocks, and participate meaningfully in supply-chain and governance arrangements. The World Bank's value-chain literature further supports this position by showing that productive participation in value chains depends on access to inputs, technology, markets, finance, and enabling institutions (World Bank, 2020). In this study, the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans is conceptualised as the extent to which Nigeria's solid minerals policy supports their raw-material access, income stability, productive capacity, market linkages, and inclusion in the mineral governance framework

2.2 Empirical Review

Empirical studies on mineral governance and artisanal production show that policy reforms do not automatically translate into improved livelihoods for local actors. Hilson and McQuilken (2014), in their review of four decades of support for artisanal and small-scale mining in sub-Saharan Africa, argue that many formalisation interventions have been too focused on licensing and regulation, while paying insufficient attention to finance, technology, market access, and poverty reduction. Their finding is relevant to this study because it suggests that formal policy recognition alone may not improve the welfare of actors operating within mineral value chains.

In Nigeria, Otoijamun et al. (2021) examined the sustainability of artisanal and small-scale mining of barite in Nasarawa State. The study reviewed existing policies and government interventions, assessed field-level mining practices, and identified factors affecting the sustainability of artisanal mining operations. Their findings show that artisanal miners face challenges relating to technology, finance, productivity, environmental practice, and institutional support. Although the study focused on barite mining rather than brass-smithing, it provides useful evidence that mineral-sector reforms in Nigeria are often weakened by poor implementation and limited support for small-scale operators.

Financial exclusion is another recurring challenge in the artisanal mineral economy. Eniowo, Kilambo, and Meyer (2022) examined risk factors limiting access to formal financing among artisanal and small-scale mining operators in Nigeria. Their study found that ASM operators are often constrained by lack of formal documentation, weak organisational capacity, poor credit history, limited collateral, and the perceived riskiness of their activities. This finding is important for the present study because brass artisans face similar problems when attempting to access working capital for raw materials, tools, and production expansion. Where finance remains inaccessible, artisans may continue to depend on informal suppliers and small-scale production methods.

The governance dimension is also central to the literature. Olujobi and Irumekhai (2024), in their legal analysis of illicit mining operations in Nigeria, show that weak oversight, ineffective enforcement, and regulatory gaps continue to undermine the proper management of the mining sector. Their study is relevant because illicit and informal mineral flows can distort prices, weaken traceability, and reduce the possibility of building stable supply linkages between miners and downstream users. For brass artisans, such governance weaknesses may translate into unstable raw-material supply, dependence on middlemen, and limited access to formal mineral markets.

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The Nigerian solid minerals sector has also been examined in relation to economic diversification and national development. Ifem et al. (2021), in their JEAR study, assessed the impact of the 2017 Economic Recovery and Growth Plan on Nigeria's solid minerals industry. They found that despite government efforts to use the sector as a tool for diversification, the industry remained constrained by weak implementation, limited productivity, and insufficient contribution to economic growth. This finding supports the argument that policy ambition alone is not enough; implementation must connect sector reforms to productive actors across the value chain.

Evidence from studies on indigenous crafts also shows that traditional production systems depend heavily on skills transfer, material availability, and local market conditions. Research on traditional crafts in Bida and Gusau indicates that apprenticeship and informal knowledge transmission remain central to craft sustainability. However, such craft systems can become vulnerable where access to raw materials, technology, and market support is weak. This insight is relevant to Bida brass-smithing because the craft depends not only on inherited skills but also on a functioning supply system for metal inputs.

Taken together, the empirical literature suggests that mineral-sector reforms in Nigeria and across sub-Saharan Africa are often constrained by weak implementation, limited finance, poor technology, informal supply networks, and inadequate institutional coordination. However, most of these studies focus on artisanal miners, mining governance, illegal mining, finance, and national economic performance. They provide limited evidence on downstream indigenous manufacturing actors, such as brass artisans, whose livelihoods depend on mineral inputs but who are not usually treated as central actors within the mineral governance framework.

2.3 Gap in Literature

Existing scholarship on Nigeria's solid minerals sector has provided important insights into diversification, artisanal mining, formalisation, finance, illicit mining, and mineral governance. Studies such as Hilson and McQuilken (2014), Otoijamun et al. (2021), Eniowo et al. (2022), Ifem et al. (2021), and Olujobi and Irumekhai (2024) show that policy reforms in the mineral sector often face implementation challenges relating to finance, technology, regulatory coordination, informality, and weak local value addition.

However, much of the existing literature remains focused on upstream extraction, national-level sector performance, or general artisanal and small-scale mining populations. Limited attention has been given to downstream indigenous producers who depend on mineral inputs for livelihood and production. In particular, indigenous brass artisans in Bida, Niger State, remain underrepresented in empirical and policy-oriented studies, despite their dependence on copper, brass, aluminium-based materials, and other mineral-related inputs.

This creates an important knowledge gap. Existing studies rarely examine how solid minerals policy translates into workshop-level outcomes such as raw-material affordability, income stability, productive capacity, access to finance, market participation, and inclusion in formal governance structures. There is also limited sub-national evidence on how policy reforms affect indigenous craft industries that operate within mineral value chains but outside the formal mining space.

This study addresses that gap by examining the influence of Nigeria's solid minerals policy on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State. It contributes to the literature by shifting attention from extraction alone to downstream mineral-dependent livelihoods, and by linking national policy objectives to the lived economic realities of indigenous artisans.

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2.4 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Capability Approach and Global Value Chain (GVC) theory. The two theories are considered appropriate because the study examines both the welfare outcomes of indigenous brass artisans and the structure of the mineral supply system within which they operate. While the Capability Approach explains economic empowerment at the artisan level, GVC theory explains the supply-chain and governance conditions that shape access to mineral-based raw materials.

The Capability Approach, associated mainly with Sen (1999), views development as the expansion of people's real freedoms and opportunities to achieve the kind of lives they value. It argues that development should not be measured only by income, but also by people's ability to access productive resources, participate in economic activities, make choices, and convert available opportunities into meaningful livelihood outcomes. Robeyns (2017) explains the Capability Approach as a broad evaluative framework for assessing wellbeing, freedom and social justice, while Alkire (2002) shows how the approach can be applied to poverty reduction and development analysis.

In this study, the Capability Approach is used to assess whether Nigeria's solid minerals policy has expanded the practical opportunities available to indigenous brass artisans in Niger State. The relevant capabilities include access to affordable raw materials, access to finance, income stability, improved production capacity, market participation and improved standard of living. This means that the study does not judge policy influence merely by the existence of laws, programmes or institutions. Rather, it asks whether such policy arrangements have improved the actual conditions under which brass artisans produce, earn income and sustain their livelihoods. However, the Capability Approach alone does not fully explain why artisans may lack access to raw materials or why policy benefits may not reach them. For this reason, the study also adopts Global Value Chain theory.

Global Value Chain (GVC) theory: GVC theory examines how production systems are organised across different actors, how power is distributed within supply chains, and how governance structures determine access, upgrading and value capture. Gereffi, Humphrey and Sturgeon (2005) developed a major framework for explaining governance patterns in global value chains, showing that participation in a value chain depends on coordination, power relations, supplier capacity and the complexity of transactions.

Within the context of this study, GVC theory explains the position of brass artisans within the wider solid minerals value chain. Brass artisans depend on mineral-related inputs such as brass, copper and aluminium-based materials, yet they often operate outside formal mining, processing and supply institutions. Where the value chain is dominated by informal intermediaries, weak mineral buying systems, limited beneficiation capacity and poor institutional coordination, artisans may be unable to secure affordable and reliable raw materials. This weakens their production capacity and limits the value they can capture from their craft.

The integration of both theories provides a clearer analytical framework for the study. The Capability Approach explains what should improve if policy is effective: raw-material access, income stability, production capacity, finance, market participation and livelihood security. GVC theory explains why those outcomes may or may not improve by focusing on supply-chain structure, institutional coordination, intermediary dominance, market access and value-chain inclusion. In other words, the Capability Approach captures the empowerment outcome, while GVC theory captures the structural pathway through which policy is expected to influence that outcome.

Accordingly, the study applies the combined framework as follows: Nigeria's solid minerals policy is treated as the institutional intervention; the mineral value chain is treated as the transmission channel; and economic

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empowerment is treated as the expected outcome for brass artisans. If policy implementation improves formal raw-material supply, strengthens market linkages, reduces dependence on informal intermediaries and supports artisan participation, then the capabilities of brass artisans are expected to improve. Conversely, where the value chain remains fragmented and artisans remain excluded from formal supply and governance arrangements, policy influence is likely to be weak, even if the policy framework exists on paper.

This theoretical position is important because it prevents the study from making a simplistic causal claim that policy alone determines the welfare of brass artisans. Instead, it allows the study to examine how policy influence is mediated by structural factors such as raw-material supply, access to finance, technology, market demand, intermediary control and institutional coordination. The combined framework therefore directly supports the study's research questions, hypotheses, analysis of findings and policy recommendations.

3. Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-methods descriptive research design to examine the influence of Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State. The design was appropriate because the study required both quantitative evidence from artisans and qualitative explanations from relevant institutional and sectoral stakeholders.

The study was conducted in Bida Local Government Area, specifically in Tswata-Mukun, Dokodza, and Gbongbofu wards, which are major brass-smithing clusters. The population for the quantitative component comprised 275 registered and non-registered brass artisans identified through artisan association records and local cluster contacts. The inclusion of non-registered artisans was necessary because many indigenous craft producers operate outside formal association structures.

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula:

$$n = N / [1 + N(e)^2]$$

Where: n is the sample size, N is the population size and e is the precision level. Given a population of 275 artisans and a precision level of 0.03, the sample size was calculated as:

$$n = 275 / [1 + 275(0.03)^2]$$

$$n = 275 / [1 + 275(0.0009)]$$

$$n = 275 / 1.2475$$

$$n = 220$$

Therefore, 220 questionnaires were administered. Out of these, 215 were retrieved and found usable, giving a response rate of 97.7%. The sample was proportionally distributed across the three wards: Tswata-Mukun, 78 respondents; Dokodza, 67 respondents; and Gbongbofu, 75 respondents.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was used. Bida was purposively selected because of its historical association with brass-smithing, while the three wards were selected because they are major production clusters. Respondents were selected through simple random sampling from available artisan lists, while snowball identification was used to include non-registered artisans. For the qualitative component, seven key informants were purposively selected from relevant institutions and stakeholder groups, including the Federal Ministry of Mines and Steel Development, Niger State Ministry of Mineral Resources, Mineral Resources and Environmental Management Committee, Raw Materials Research and Development Council, Miners Association of Nigeria, mineral buying centre actors, and brass artisan leadership.

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Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires and key informant interviews. The questionnaire was designed on a five-point Likert scale and covered raw-material affordability, access to credit, income improvement, production expansion, standard of living, policy awareness, inclusion in policy processes, governance support, access to mineral buying centres, and reliance on intermediaries. The interviews provided explanations on policy implementation, institutional coordination, raw-material supply, financing, beneficiation, and artisan inclusion. Secondary data were obtained from policy documents, government reports, journal articles, and relevant publications.

The analytical model of the study is expressed as:

$$EE = f(SMP, MVCI, X)$$

Where:

EE = Economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans

SMP = Solid minerals policy implementation

MVCI = Mineral value-chain integration

X = Other structural factors such as market demand, technology, finance, and institutional coordination

Quantitative data were analysed using IBM SPSS version 26. Frequencies, percentages, and mean scores were used to summarise responses. Mean scores were interpreted using the following thresholds: 1.00–1.80 = strongly disagree; 1.81–2.60 = disagree; 2.61–3.40 = neutral; 3.41–4.20 = agree; and 4.21–5.00 = strongly agree. Instrument reliability was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha, with 0.70 adopted as the acceptable threshold.

The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square test of goodness of fit, specified as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum [(O - E)^2 / E]$$

Where:

χ^2 = chi-square statistic

O = observed frequency

E = expected frequency

The null hypothesis was rejected where the p-value was less than 0.05. Since the study relied on cross-sectional perception data, the test was interpreted as evidence of statistical association rather than direct causality.

Qualitative data were analysed thematically through familiarization, coding, theme development, and interpretation. The major themes included raw-material access, policy implementation gaps, institutional coordination, financing constraints, intermediary dominance, beneficiation limitations, and exclusion from governance structures. The qualitative findings were used to explain and triangulate the quantitative results.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval

Table 4.1: Distribution and Retrieval of Questionnaires by Ward

Ward	Target Population	Sample Size	Returned	Not Returned
Tswata-Mukun	97	78	78	0
Dokodza	84	67	64	3
Gbongbofu	94	75	73	2
Total	275	220	215	5

Source: Field Survey (2025); SPSS 26.0 Output.

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Table 4.1 shows that 215 out of 220 questionnaires were retrieved, representing a response rate of 97.7 percent. Tswata-Mukun recorded full retrieval, while Dokodza and Gbongbofu recorded only minimal non-response. The high response rate provides a reliable basis for the analysis.

4.2 Demographic and workshop Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.2: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 215)

Variable / Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	215	100.0
Female	0	0.0
Age Distribution		
15–25 years	29	13.5
26–35 years	61	28.4
36–45 years	63	29.3
46–55 years	44	20.5
56 years and above	18	8.4
Educational Background		
No Formal Education	5	2.3
Primary	25	11.6
Secondary	61	28.4
Higher Education	46	21.4
Vocational / Trade	78	36.3
Years of Experience in Brass-Smithing		
Less than 5 years	28	13.0
5–10 years	56	26.0
11–20 years	86	40.0
21–30 years	22	10.2
31 years and above	23	10.7
Monthly Production Volume		
Below 10 units	52	24.2
11–30 units	71	33.0
31–60 units	41	19.1
61 units and above	51	23.7
Primary Channel for Obtaining Raw Materials		
Licensed mineral trader	36	16.7
Artisanal miner directly	28	13.0

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Variable / Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Mineral Buying Centre	18	8.4
Recycled scrap dealer	40	18.6
Imported materials	93	43.3
Registration Status with Brass-Smithing Association		
Registered Member	171	79.5
Non-Registered	44	20.5

Source: Field Survey (2025); SPSS 26.0 Output.

Table 4.2 shows that all respondents were male, reflecting the male-dominated character of brass-smithing in the study area. Most respondents were within the economically active age group, with 57.7 percent falling between 26 and 45 years. Vocational or trade education was the largest educational category, accounting for 36.3 percent, while 40.0 percent of respondents had 11–20 years of experience. This suggests that the respondents had sufficient practical knowledge of the craft and its raw material challenges.

The table also shows that production is largely small to medium scale, as 57.2 percent of respondents produced between below 10 and 30 units monthly. Imported materials constituted the largest sourcing channel at 43.3 percent, followed by recycled scrap dealers at 18.6 percent. Only 8.4 percent of respondents identified Mineral Buying Centres as their primary source. This pattern already suggests limited reliance on formal mineral supply channels.

4.3 Influence of Policy on Economic Empowerment of Indigenous Brass Artisans

Table 4.3: Influence of Policy on Economic Empowerment of Indigenous Brass Artisans (N = 215)

Indicator	Dominant Response	Mean	Decision
Raw-material affordability	Disagree (72.8%)	1.94	Disagree
Access to credit	Strongly disagree (53.9%)	1.65	Strongly disagree
Income improvement	Strongly disagree (79.1%)	1.26	Strongly disagree
Production expansion	Disagree (46.6%)	1.64	Strongly disagree
Standard of living	Strongly disagree (84.0%)	1.24	Strongly disagree
Grand Mean		1.54	Strongly disagree

Source: Field Survey (2026); SPSS 26.0 Output.

Table 4.3 shows that respondents generally disagreed that Nigeria’s Solid Minerals Policy has improved their economic empowerment. The grand mean of 1.54 falls within the “strongly disagree” range, indicating weak perceived policy impact on artisan-level economic outcomes. The lowest mean scores were recorded for standard of living (1.24), income improvement (1.26), production expansion (1.64), and access to credit (1.65). This suggests that the policy has not significantly translated into improved income, affordable inputs, financial access, or productive expansion for indigenous brass artisans in the study area.

Qualitative evidence supports this result. Key informants repeatedly noted that the major constraints were not the absence of policy, but weak implementation, poor access to formal raw-material channels, inadequate technology, limited finance, and low integration of artisans into government-supported mineral development programmes.

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One respondent observed that although mineral buying centres exist, many artisans still depend on cheaper scrap inputs because formal supply channels are either costly, inaccessible, or poorly linked to their production needs. Another respondent noted that local mineral production has not substantially improved artisans’ access to aluminium, copper, and zinc because miners often prioritise larger buyers and external markets.

These findings suggest that the policy has created a formal framework for sector development, but its benefits have not sufficiently reached indigenous brass artisans. The result also shows that economic empowerment is constrained by wider structural factors, including raw-material costs, weak domestic processing, limited credit support, and the continued dominance of informal intermediaries.

4.4 Challenges Hindering Integration into the Mineral Governance Framework

Table 4.4: Challenges Hindering Integration of Brass Artisans into the Mineral Governance Framework (N = 215)

Indicator	Dominant Response	Mean	Decision
Policy awareness	Disagree (58.2%)	2.43	Disagree
Inclusion in policy processes	Strongly disagree (54.4%)	1.81	Disagree
Governance support	Strongly agree (27.2%)	3.01	Neutral
Lack of buying centres	Strongly agree (73.3%)	4.33	Strongly agree
Reliance on intermediaries	Strongly agree (79.1%)	4.64	Strongly agree
Grand Mean		3.24	Neutral

Source: Field Survey (2026); SPSS 26.0 Output.

Table 4.4 shows that the most serious integration challenges are structural. Respondents strongly agreed that reliance on intermediaries was a major challenge, with a mean score of 4.64. Lack of effective access to mineral buying centres also recorded a high mean score of 4.33. These two indicators suggest that artisans are weakly connected to formal mineral supply systems and remain dependent on informal or intermediary-controlled channels for raw materials.

The results also show low inclusion of artisans in policy processes, with a mean score of 1.81, and weak policy awareness, with a mean score of 2.43. This indicates that many artisans are not sufficiently informed about relevant policy opportunities and are not meaningfully involved in mineral-sector decision-making. Governance support recorded a neutral mean score of 3.01, suggesting that respondents neither clearly affirmed nor rejected the existence of institutional support. This may reflect the presence of formal institutions on paper, but limited practical benefits at the artisan level.

The qualitative interviews reinforce this interpretation. Key informants identified bureaucratic bottlenecks, weak coordination between federal and state institutions, limited beneficiation facilities, inadequate data on artisan clusters, poor access to loans and grants, and the dominance of middlemen as major barriers to effective integration. One respondent noted that governance discussions often take place at federal and state levels without sufficient engagement with artisans in Bida. Another observed that the absence of local beneficiation and analytical centres reduces the ability of Niger State to convert mineral endowments into direct benefits for local producers.

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Overall, the findings show that the integration problem is not merely informational; it is also institutional and structural. Brass artisans remain weakly connected to formal mineral governance arrangements, and this limits their access to raw materials, finance, technology, and market opportunities.

4.5 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square test of goodness of fit at a 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis where the p-value was less than 0.05; otherwise, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Nigeria’s Solid Minerals Policy has no significant influence on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State.

Table 4.5: Chi-Square Test for Hypothesis One

Variable	χ^2	df	p-value	Decision
Empowerment indicators	182.6	4	<0.05	Reject H ₀₁

Source: Field Survey (2026); SPSS 26.0 Output.

Table 4.5 shows that the chi-square value for the empowerment indicators was 182.6, with a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This indicates a statistically significant association between Nigeria’s Solid Minerals Policy and the economic empowerment indicators examined in the study. However, the direction of the responses, as shown in Table 4.3, suggests that the perceived influence has been weak and largely non-supportive in terms of raw-material affordability, access to credit, income improvement, production expansion, and standard of living.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There are no significant challenges hindering the effective integration of indigenous brass artisans into the solid minerals governance framework in Niger State.

Table 4.6 : Chi-Square Test for Hypothesis 2

Variable	χ^2	df	p-value	Decision
Integration challenges	205.3	4	<0.05	Reject H ₀₂

Source: Field Survey (2026); SPSS 26.0 Output.

Table 4.6 shows that the chi-square value for integration challenges was 205.3, with a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected. This confirms that significant challenges hinder the integration of indigenous brass artisans into the solid minerals governance framework. The main challenges, as shown in Table 4.4, include reliance on intermediaries, weak access to mineral buying centres, low policy awareness, and limited inclusion in policy processes.

4.6 Discussion of Findings

The findings show that Nigeria’s Solid Minerals Policy has not translated into strong economic empowerment outcomes for indigenous brass artisans in Niger State. The grand mean of 1.54 indicates weak perceived improvement in raw-material affordability, access to credit, income, production expansion, and standard of living. This supports Hilson and McQuilken’s (2014) argument that formalisation policies in artisanal and small-scale mining often improve regulatory visibility without necessarily improving livelihoods. It also agrees with

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Otoijamun et al. (2021), who identified weak finance, technology, productivity, and institutional support as major constraints to sustainable artisanal mining outcomes in Nigeria.

The finding is also consistent with the Capability Approach, which argues that development should be assessed by people's real ability to convert opportunities into valued livelihood outcomes, not merely by the existence of policies or resources (Sen, 1999; Robeyns, 2017). In this study, the policy has not sufficiently expanded artisans' practical capabilities to access affordable raw materials, secure credit, improve income, expand production, or enhance living standards.

The findings further show that weak integration into formal mineral supply systems remains a major constraint. Reliance on intermediaries recorded the highest mean score of 4.64, while weak access to mineral buying centres recorded 4.33. This aligns with Global Value Chain Theory, which explains that producers capture value only when they are effectively linked to input supply, processing, finance, technology, markets, and governance structures (Gereffi et al., 2005). The continued dependence of brass artisans on informal intermediaries, imported materials, and scrap dealers indicates weak value-chain integration and limited local value capture.

These results are consistent with Eniowo et al. (2022), who found that weak documentation, poor organisation, and limited access to finance constrain formal participation among artisanal mining actors in Nigeria. They also agree with Olujobi and Irumekhai (2024), who observed that weak regulation and informal mineral flows undermine traceability and effective governance in the Nigerian mining sector.

Overall, the findings confirm the relevance of combining the Capability Approach and Global Value Chain Theory. The Capability Approach explains the weak empowerment outcomes, while Global Value Chain Theory explains the structural reasons for those outcomes. The study therefore shows that improving the economic condition of brass artisans requires more than policy pronouncements; it requires practical mechanisms for raw-material access, finance, technology support, market linkage, and inclusion in mineral governance structures.

5.1 Conclusion

The study examined the influence of Nigeria's Solid Minerals Policy on the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State. The findings show that although the policy framework promotes formalisation, value addition, and inclusive mineral-sector development, these objectives have not sufficiently translated into improved workshop-level outcomes for brass artisans. The artisans still face unstable raw-material supply, high input costs, weak access to credit, limited production expansion, and poor integration into formal mineral supply and governance structures.

The study further shows that the main challenge is not the absence of policy, but the weak transmission of policy benefits to downstream indigenous producers. From the perspective of the Capability Approach, the policy has not sufficiently expanded the practical opportunities available to brass artisans to improve their livelihoods. From the Global Value Chain perspective, the artisans remain weakly linked to formal raw-material supply, processing, finance, technology, and market systems. The study therefore concludes that meaningful empowerment of indigenous brass artisans requires stronger institutional coordination and deliberate inclusion of artisans in Nigeria's solid minerals value chain.

5.2 Recommendations

First, to improve the economic empowerment of indigenous brass artisans in Niger State, the Federal Ministry of Solid Minerals Development, in collaboration with the Niger State Ministry of Mineral Resources, Raw Materials Research and Development Council (RMRDC), SMEDAN, Bank of Industry (BOI), and Bida Local Government

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Council, should establish a targeted artisan-support framework for the Bida brass-smithing cluster. This framework should provide artisans with reliable access to affordable copper, aluminium-based materials, zinc, brass, and other relevant inputs in small and production-appropriate quantities. It should also include low-interest working capital, cooperative-based credit access, improved production tools, technical training, and product-quality enhancement support. These measures would reduce dependence on informal intermediaries, improve raw-material stability, strengthen productivity, and enhance the income-generating capacity of brass artisans. Second, to strengthen the integration of brass artisans into the solid minerals governance framework, the Federal Ministry of Solid Minerals Development, Niger State Government, Mineral Resources and Environmental Management Committee (MIREMCO), RMRDC, and relevant artisan associations should create a formal mineral–artisan linkage platform in Niger State. The platform should connect brass artisans with mineral buying centres, miners’ associations, material-processing facilities, regulatory institutions, and market-support agencies. It should also provide regular consultation, policy sensitisation, artisan data collection, and inclusion of brass artisan representatives in relevant mineral-sector programmes. Through this arrangement, government can improve institutional coordination, strengthen formal supply channels, promote beneficiation and material-processing support, and ensure that downstream indigenous producers are no longer excluded from policy implementation and value-chain opportunities.

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